

Synthesis and Biological Activities of Quinoline- and Quinaldine-8-thioglycollic Acid Thiosemicarbazide

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Several new quinoline- and quinaldine-8-thioglycollic acid thiosemicarbazides have been prepared by the reaction of quinoline- and quinaldine-8-thioglycollic acid hydrazides with various phenyl- and naphthyl-isothiocyanates. The compounds have been screened for their activity towards gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria.

THIOSEMICARBAZIDES possessing the N-C-S group have been reported to show pronounced biological activities¹. Heterocyclic thioglycollic acid thiosemicarbazides have been reported to possess various biological activities².

In view of the importance of heterocyclic thioglycollic acid thiosemicarbazides as mentioned above, we have synthesised some new heterocyclic thioglycollic acid thiosemicarbazides. We have made thiosemicarbazides of quinoline- and quinaldine-8-thioglycollic acid and all the compounds have been screened for their antibacterial activities against gram-positive and gram-negative micro-organism. Such thiosemicarbazides have been prepared by the reaction of quinoline- and quinaldine-8-thioglycollic acid hydrazides with phenyl isothiocyanate, *p*-chlorophenyl isothiocyanate, *p*-bromophenyl isothiocyanate, *p*-methylphenyl isothiocyanate, *p*-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanate, *p*-ethoxyphenyl isothiocyanate, α -naphthyl isothiocyanate and β -naphthyl isothiocyanate (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either AnalaR or extra pure (E. Merk) grade. The quinoline- and quinaldine-8-thioglycollic acid hydrazides were synthesised as mentioned in the previous communication³. A general procedure⁴ for the preparation of aryl and naphthyl isothiocyanates was adopted. Mps. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

Quinoline- and quinaldine-8-thioglycollic acid thiosemicarbazides: The isothiocyanates (0.01 mol) were refluxed on a water-bath with hydrazides of quinoline- and quinaldine-8-thioglycollic acid (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol for 3-6 h. A solid mass separated even in hot condition and the reaction mixture was cooled for complete precipitation. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from dilute alcohol.

Results and Discussion

All the thiosemicarbazides of quinoline- and quinaldine-8-thioglycollic acids are crystalline in nature and white in colour. The physical and spectral data of all the thiosemicarbazides are listed in Table 1.

Biological screening: All the compounds were screened against klebsiella, *S. aureus*, *S. albus*, Proteus, *E. coli* and pyocyanea bacteria using agar plate disk diffusion technique⁵.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE THIOSEMICARBAZIDES

Sl. no.	Compd.* (Mol. formula)	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)**		
					NH	C=O	C=S
1.	Qn.8.Th GL NHNHR ₁ , (C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ S ₂ O)	PhNCS	199	50	3 360sh 3 200br	1 700s 1 670m	1 170w
2.	Qn.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ , (C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₂ S ₂ OCl)	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ NCS	196	60	3 280s 3 200br	1 710s 1 675s	1 170m
3.	Qn.8.Th GL.NHNHR ₁ , (C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ S ₂ OBr)	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ NCS	200	60	3 280s 3 180m	1 710s 1 675s	1 170m
4.	Qn.8.Th GL.NHNHR ₁ , (C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ S ₂ O)	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ NCS	191	60	3 240m 3 200w	1 700s 1 680m	1 175w

(Table 1 contd.)

5.	Qn.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂)	p-MeOC ₆ H ₄ NCS	225	65	3 280s 3 190m	1 710s 1 678s	1 170m
6.	Qn.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂)	p-EtOC ₆ H ₄ NCS	206	60	3 260s 3 187s	1 710s 1 670s	1 160m
7.	Qn.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O)	α-Naphthyl- isothiocyanate	175	60	3 340m 3 200m	1 695s 1 650m	1 170m
8.	Qn.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O)	β-Naphthyl- isothiocyanate	220d	70	3 250s 3 150m	1 695m	1 165m
9.	Ql.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O)	PhNCS	190	60	3 200s 3 100s	1 690m	1 160m
10.	Ql.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ OCl)	p-ClC ₆ H ₄ NCS	194	60	3 400m 3 100m	1 690m 1 665w	1 160m
11.	Ql.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ OBr)	p-BrC ₆ H ₄ NCS	210	60	3 400m 3 100m	1 695w 1 66 w	1 165m
12.	Ql.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O)	p-MeC ₆ H ₄ NCS	181	60	3 350m 3 280m	1 650s	1 175m
13.	Ql.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O)	p-MeOC ₆ H ₄ NCS	176	50	3 350br 3 180w	1 640m	1 175m
14.	Ql.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O)	p-EtOC ₆ H ₄ NCS	212	50	3 200s 3 120s	1 695s 1 650s	1 160s
15.	Ql.8.Th.GL.NHNHR ₁ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O)	β-Naphthyl- isothiocyanate	265	60	3 200s 3 105s	1 700s	1 170m

*All compounds furnished satisfactory C, H and N analyses; Qn.8.Th.GL.NHNHR₁=quinoline-8-thioglycollic acid thiosemicarbazide, Ql.8.Th.GL.NHNHR₁=quinoline-8-thioglycollic acid thiosemicarbazide. **s=strong, m=medium, br=broad, sh=shoulder, w=weak.

Compound sl. no. 9 was found inactive against *S. aureus* while all others were moderately active (zone of inhibition 6–8 mm). The compound sl. no. 11 possessed the highest sensitivity against *E. coli* (zone of inhibition 10–12 mm). The compound sl. nos. 7 and 9 had the least inhibition against *E. coli* and klebsiella.

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